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Identity through Violence: A Study of “An Introduction” by Kamala Das

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Abstract

Kamala Das’ “An Introduction” focuses on the dynamics of identity and violence in the formation of female identity in a male dominated world. In the poem, the interrelation of identity and violence has been brought to fore to deconstruct established roles, cultural practices, and ascribed identities only to formulate new ones through violent measures. This paper argues that the speaker’s quest paves the way to establish her own identity as an individual as she overcomes the violent suffering, deprivation and exploitation while disrupting the established social norms of a patriarchal society by identifying herself with the dominant male ‘I’. This unique perspective allows the readers to better understand the society, to locate issues of identity and its associated violence.

Keywords: Identity, violence, domination, culture, Kamala Das.

Identity revolves around different relationships such as those between the personal and the social, or those between self and others. It is very difficult to provide a simple answer to the question of who one is, because the markers of identity are multiple: racial, linguistic, political, gender, professional, cultural, etcetera; and thus, each and every person is unique. A sense of identity can be a source not merely of pride and joy, but also of strength and confidence. And yet, identity can also kill – and kill with abandon.¹ Identity is inseparably connected with violence. Building identity and exploring different aspects of it to introduce oneself is an innate

¹ Amartya Sen, *Identity and Violence: The Illusions of Destiny*, (London and New York: Penguin, 2006). p. 15.

impulse of humans, the process bearing multi-layered violence within it. Violence enters and consumes our literature because it produces a cathartic effect on us. As writers imitate life, they depict our fears regarding manifestations of violence in their works; and recently issues of identity politics and violence have taken the center stage of literary discourse. This article argues that Kamala Das' "An Introduction" is a poem that uses the relationship between identity and violence to deconstruct established roles, cultural practices, and ascribed identities to construct new ones through violent measures.

Identity offers a way of thinking about the links between the personal and the social; of the meeting place of the psychological and the social, of the psyche and the society.² On the other hand, most people usually think of violence as the implementation of physical force, and sometimes language, against someone with the intention of causing harm, either physical or psychological. For example, Kit Christensen defines violence as the direct or indirect infliction of injury on someone or something by some agent.³ Louis Silverstein defines violence as human behavior, overt or covert, institutionalised or non-institutionalised, involving one person or a group of persons, with the result being the inflicting of suffering upon another human being by violating his body and/or property.⁴ But Galtung claims that violence is present when human beings are being influenced so that their actual somatic and mental realisations are below their potential realisations. He accepts that on some conceptions, violence must be physical and must result in physical damage at the hands of an agent who intends that to be the consequence, but rejects such conceptions as too narrow. Rather, he defines violence as the cause of the difference between the potential and the actual, between what could have been and what is,

² Kath Woodward, *Understanding Identity*, London: Arnold, 2002. p. vii.

³ Kit R. Christensen, *Nonviolence, Peace and Justice: A Philosophical Introduction*, Ontario: Broadview Press, 2010. pp. 31–32

⁴ Louis Silverstein, 'The Nature of Violence: A Teaching Guide', *The History Teacher*, May, 1971, Vol. 4, No. 4 (May, 1971), p. 68

adding that it increases the distance between the potential and the actual, and it impedes the decrease of this distance.⁵

As the name suggests, Kamala Das' "An Introduction" introduces the speaker as an individual, while it tracks the experience of the speaker's attempt in establishing her identity. The poem displays the speaker's search for identity and self-discovery while reviewing the different stages of her growth from a child to a woman. It also serves as a commentary on the various constraints that a woman is subjected to, thus denying her the opportunity to establish her own identity as a woman and as a human being. She shares her experiences of the violent environment that shaped her and constructed her identities. Then again, her violent protests and rejections of those identities to form a new one are also visible, along with her resistance against her hostile surrounding. As the readers gradually become familiar with the speaker, their understanding of herself and surrounding offers an insight into the three major dimensions of the speaker's identity. There is, firstly, the identity that is formed in relation with others, with whom the speaker does not share solidarity. Secondly, the speaker herself is continuously in the process of forming identity, which matures towards the end of the poem. Lastly, the speaker recognises a universal identity and identifies herself with it.

"An Introduction" is a poem very bluntly put, yet sharply piercing, with rebellion at its core and juxtaposition as its crust. The poem begins with the indoctrination of patriarchal power structure into a child, and traces that child's development, struggles, predicaments, and limitations imposed upon her. Then the poem showcases her struggle for overcoming these limitations, by building, destroying and re-building her identity at different stages of her life. Finally, the poem acknowledges, by the end, the speaker's state as a fully grown woman/person. Along this journey, the speaker, and with her the reader, becomes aware of the presence of violence as the poem harbors strong themes of limitation, violence, and feminism.

⁵ Johan Galtung, 'Violence, Peace, and Peace Research', *Journal of Peace Research*, 1969, Vol. 6, No. 3 (1969), pp. 168-169.

Throughout the whole poem, the reader can recognise instances of violence in its various forms. But, the definition of violence is important to locate and realise these instances. It is rather difficult to assign a single phrasing to a multi-dimensional phenomenon like violence. John Swomley, Jr. views violence not only as the harmful use of force against persons but as social structures which cause the oppression of human beings.⁶ Limiting one's potentials through any means is a severely violent act according to Galtung,⁷ and in the poem violence is inflicted on the speaker by placing limitations on her, and she fights back by dismantling socio-cultural practices, roles and norms that are already in existence. Also, breaking establishments, however violent their very existence may be, in order to reach one's full potential requires a certain amount of force, whether physical, mental or emotional, or of any other kind for that matter; which is applied against another party. Thus, this process of resistance is also very violent in nature, as Kit Christensen defines it.⁸

The theme of limitation (and overcoming them) is an overarching one in this poem; with the points of limitation found being based on power, authority, and gender. The limitation placed on linguistic expression is obvious, and it can be interpreted as a limitation on the speaker's freedom of choice. So, when the speaker is denied her choice of language, she is, in fact, deprived of using language in her own way to express herself. Robbing a person of his/her power to use language is definitely a violent act as linguistic exchanges can be considered as a relationship of symbolic power where the power relations between the speakers are actualised.⁹ Restricted from taking major decisions in her life by herself, the speaker has no authority over her own self. And the examples of limitation placed on her due to her

⁶Louis Silverstein, 'The Nature of Violence: A Teaching Guide', *The History Teacher*, May, 1971, Vol. 4, No. 4 (May, 1971), p. 67

⁷Johan Galtung, 'Violence, Peace, and Peace Research', *Journal of Peace Research*, 1969, Vol. 6, No. 3 (1969), pp. 168-169.

⁸Kit R. Christensen, *Nonviolence, Peace and Justice: A Philosophical Introduction*, Ontario: Broadview Press, 2010. pp. 31-32

⁹ Pierre Bourdieu, *Language and Symbolic Power*, Harvard University Press, 1991, p. 37.

gender are too many. She ceaselessly continues to receive instructions regarding her dress, profession, attitude, behavior, and identity because she is a female in a patriarchy; and these restrictions truncate her potentials. According to the definition of Galtung, such imposition of limitation is a violent act.¹⁰ Again, the speaker, as a female, struggles against the ever-imposing “them” to realise her potentials, as well as establish and enact her rights; and in the process, she creates a rupture in the existing system/tradition and creates inroad into them by violating the very instructions she was given. She consciously ignores her womanliness, cuts her hair and dresses up in her brother’s clothes, challenging the traditional gender roles. So, her resistance is violent too. The cutting of her hair is a violent act in itself; and cross-dressing, by definition, troubles the assumed binary relation between ‘men’ and ‘women’ and exposes that gender, the socially constructed identities such as masculine and feminine, is labile.¹¹

The very beginning of the poem holds subtle instances of violence within it. The speaker clarifies her stance regarding politics in the first sentence, claiming that

“I don’t know politics but I know the names
Of those in power, and can repeat them like
Days of week, or names of months, beginning with
Nehru...”

A scrutiny of the speaker’s tone in the sentence, makes it clear that she has little regard about politics and politicians, the ones holding state power. Her use of the number of days or months may indicate her lack of reverence for the politicians, and her tone shows a complete disregard for them. This rejection can be taken as a violent act, because according to Amartya Sen, a passive rejection of someone’s existence can also be a violent disrespect

¹⁰Johan Galtung, ‘Violence, Peace, and Peace Research’, *Journal of Peace Research*, 1969, Vol. 6, No. 3 (1969), pp. 168-169.

¹¹ Bennett Capers, “Cross Dressing and the Criminal”, *Yale JL & Human*. 20 (2008): 1. Pp. 4-5.

having deep psychological effect.¹² By acknowledging, or boasting, her ignorance about the politicians, the speaker is in effect attacking a group of people to whom that attention, and the power and control resulting from it combined, is the very essence of their existence. The very utterance “I don’t know politics...” makes the reader aware of her violent yet passive rejection of the political structure. But it can be interpreted from another point of view, too. These lines display the binary roles played by culture and identity in shaping the speaker. Culture as a constrictive framework is socially imposed on the individual by various centres of power, and it guides an individual towards a particular form of identity. These lines can be read as an example of how patriarchy creates a hegemonic culture that neither expects nor accepts women knowing politics, by keeping them, both individually and collectively, excluded from the centres of power. The fact that the speaker can only ‘repeat’ the names of ‘those in power’ can be easily interpreted as a limiting act on women, to subjugate them.¹³ If it is the hegemonic culture that sidelines the speaker as a female and the speaker grows up to accept it, then this submissive identity of the speaker is the direct result of the violent limitation by patriarchy. But if it is interpreted as a rejection of the male dominated power centres, it can be assumed that the speaker is using a violent act of her own to assert her identity.

As the speaker discovers the identities that she possesses, but cannot change, she owns these identities, boldly declaring her brown color, Indian origin and linguistic inheritance

“... I speak three languages, write in
Two, dream in one...”

It is easy to guess the languages she speaks and writes in. But, the last part of this sentence leaves the reader guessing. The language she dreams in is

¹²Amartya Sen, ”The Nature and Nurture of Violence”, *Peace and Democratic Society*”, Open Book Publishers, 2011, p. 61.

¹³ M. Gopinath and A.S. Raagavi, “The cultural influence as expressed by Kamala Das in her Feministic poem ‘An Introduction’” *Malaya Journal of Matematik*, Vol. 5, No. 2, 4131-4133, 2020.

the only language in which she can express her true self; it is her *Ecriture Feminine*.¹⁴ While her use of English in writing poems is seen by the critics as a betrayal against her mother tongue, her retaliation is immediate, strong, and violent, stamping her authority over her choices of using language:

“... Don’t write in English, they said,
English is not your mother-tongue. Why not leave
Me alone, critics, friends, visiting cousins,
Every one of you? Why not let me speak in
Any language I like? The language I speak
Becomes mine, its distortions, its queernesses
All mine, mine alone...”

Here the speaker vehemently refuses to conform to culturally acceptable language and embraces her own language with all its distortions and queerness. This reply may look like a pleading, but the anticlimactic arrangement of her addressees makes the readers understand the violent tone of the speaker. But the speaker resorts to this only because she takes the suggestion to stop writing in her preferred language as an act of violence against her. This assertion of her claim over her use of language is necessary for her, because it makes her who she is. In her case, taking authority over her linguistic expression is a protest against the set guidelines, as she refuses to be guided by her critics who want to make a stereotype of a writer out of her. As Bourdieu sees language as an instrument of power and action, and a form of domination in itself,¹⁵ the speaker’s linguistic expression being thwarted here becomes a form of violence; so becomes her bold response to them, declaring her ability to use and distort language. On one hand there is an agent, or a group of agents trying to suppress a person’s linguistic expression, an act of limitation which increases the distance between the potential and the actual that can be

¹⁴Hélène Cixous. Keith Cohen and Paula Cohen (trns). "The laugh of the Medusa." *Signs: Journal of women in culture and society* 1, no. 4 (1976)

¹⁵J. Daniel Schubert, "Suffering/Symbolic Violence", in *Pierre Bourdieu:Key Concepts*, Grenfell, Michael James, ed. Routledge, 2014.p.183.

called violent according to Galtung;¹⁶ on the other hand there is the speaker, with the authority to distort something the agents hold pure and dear, which, if executed, may result in violence by the definition formulated by Christensen.¹⁷ But it is quite interesting to note that those who harbour such sentiment regarding the use of a particular language, are themselves victims of symbolic violence,¹⁸ which is the effect of a hierarchy set up by the dominant groups of society which, through normalisation, comes to be perceived as legitimate. Members of the dominant classes need only go about their normal daily lives, adhering to the rules of the system that provides them their positions of privilege. Hierarchies and systems of domination are then reproduced to the extent that the dominant and the dominated perceive these systems to be legitimate and thus think and act in their own best interests within the context of the system itself.¹⁹ So, when the critics and friends, and visiting cousins try to limit the speaker to the use of her mother tongue only, they submit themselves to a linguistic hierarchy. But, as the speaker is aware of her power to use any language she chooses, the symbolic violence is not being incited on her. Rather, as the “dominant” group is enforcing these arbitrary rules as legitimate ones, they are in the receiving end of the violence.

“... It is half English, half
Indian, funny perhaps, but it is honest,
It is as human as I am human, don't
You see?...”

Here, she explains the nature of her language, deeming it to be “human language”. She is supporting her claims to express herself in her own language, bringing attention to two fundamental characteristics of

¹⁶Johan Galtung, ‘Violence, Peace, and Peace Research’, *Journal of Peace Research*, 1969, Vol. 6, No. 3 (1969), pp. 168-169.

¹⁷Kit R. Christensen, *Nonviolence, Peace and Justice: A Philosophical Introduction*, Ontario: Broadview Press, 2010. pp. 31–32

¹⁸J. Daniel Schubert, “Suffering/symbolic Violence”, in *Pierre Bourdieu:Key Concepts*, Grenfell, Michael James, ed. Routledge, 2014, p. 184.

¹⁹J. Daniel Schubert, “Suffering/symbolic Violence”, in *Pierre Bourdieu:Key Concepts*, Grenfell, Michael James, ed. Routledge, 2014.pp.183-4.

language: firstly, language is a uniquely human phenomenon; and secondly, language has life. She is protesting against the suppressors here, contrasting the lifelessness and rigidity of the suppressors' obstruction and their structure-bound thinking with the liveliness of language. She goes on to explain the function of her language, and its usefulness, and in the process, calls her critics mindless and insensible. This verbal abuse amounts to violence as a tool of resistance, as language here becomes the instrument of power and action:

“... It voices my joys, my longings, my
 Hopes, and it is useful to me as cawing
 Is to crows or roaring to the lions, it
 Is human speech, the speech of the mind that is
 Here and not there, a mind that sees and hears and
 Is aware. ...”

The verbal abuse of the dominant group by the speaker is violent. She does so through the contrast between conscious and non-conscious beings. It is rather a euphemistic insult to the oppressors — calling them ignorant. And thus, through this complete set of images and the process of contrast and comparison, she proves that the dominant groups are merely vessels carrying out the colonial will, forced upon the Indian people decades ago.

The speaker puts the conflict between culture and her linguistic freedom to rest and goes on to deal with her female identity. With the advent of her puberty, she grows silent, perhaps being frustrated and tired from oral protests in the previous phase. She observes all that is done to her in silence.

“... I was child, and later they
 Told me I grew, for I became tall, my limbs
 Swelled and one or two places sprouted hair. ...”

The speaker describes herself as a ‘child’ but the gender-neutrality of ‘child’ does not last long. Due to swelling limbs and sprouting hair at certain places, she is told that she has grown up. As the girl’s body matures, society reacts in an increasingly hostile manner, which Beauvoir describes as the process of becoming flesh, a process whereby one comes to experience

oneself as a sexual bodily being, exposed to another's gaze.²⁰ This one-dimensional idea of growth sponsored by the male dominated society limits her boundary and puts a hindrance to her chances of exploring her potential, which, according to Galtung's definition, is an act of violence.²¹ Moreover, the speaker claims that she is "told" that she "grew". Telling is a more forceful mode of expression where it generally is not possible for the receiver to refute the suggestion. By 'telling' the speaker about her growth, the authoritative male dominated society does not leave any chance for the speaker to think otherwise, and thus limits her choices. The speaker thus becomes the victim of the patriarchal gaze. Though her growth is physical and natural, her growth is always monitored by society, under the influence of the prevalent cultural assumption. By being told that she has grown, the speaker is marginalised to the position of an object under the panoptic gaze of the society. Being limited into being just a woman, which she becomes when she is told that she has grown into it, she is married off and thus is introduced to the violence of sexual intercourse through marital rape. This intercourse can be called an act of violence because it does not seem from the poem that there was any form of consent involved on her part.

he drew a youth of sixteen into the
Bedroom and closed the door. He did not beat me
But my sad woman-body felt so beaten."

The diction used by the speaker is very indicative of the status of the protagonist as a helpless woman. The use of the words 'youth', 'drew', 'closed' and 'beat' describes what the protagonist thinks of her condition. Firstly, "a youth of sixteen," is usually helpless and unaware of her own self and sexuality. Secondly, when, she is 'drawn' into the bedroom, this image becomes disturbing; because, this very visual image can easily be equated to that of dragging cattle to the slaughterhouse. The readers do not fail to

²⁰ Simone de Beauvoir, *The Second Sex*, trs. Constance Borde and Sheila Malovany-Chevallier (New York: Vintage Books, 2011), pp 368-70.

²¹ Johan Galtung, 'Violence, Peace, and Peace Research', *Journal of Peace Research*, 1969, Vol. 6, No. 3 (1969), pp. 168-169.

notice the fact that the protagonist, though is treated as a grown woman, is not welcomed to the marital bed, rather drawn into forcefully. Thirdly, the closing of the door by the groom is a very simple indication that the protagonist is now caged under his authority, as she is now a wife. Here again, a new identity of the protagonist is formed, that of a wife, but this identity also comes at the price of her freedom, will, and body. This unwilling subjugation to the male authority is definitely considerable as an act of violence against the protagonist. It is noteworthy here that the protagonist is not aware of what to ask for at this stage of so called 'growth' in her life. She "... asked for love, not knowing what else to ask/ For...", which means she had a very romantic idea of life, with dreams for the future, but it was crushed by some violent decisions taken by the patriarchal society. And the protagonist explains her first experience with sexuality in a very negative manner when she uses the word 'beaten' to express how she felt after the first sexual intercourse, through which she is transformed into a 'woman', and enters another phase of her identity. She claims that the feeling she has afterwards is not that of a languid afterglow, rather it is that of a sad tiredness. The violent imagery of marital rape and the speaker's selection of words in describing the rape remind the readers of Simone de Beauvoir's classic statement that one is not born, rather becomes a woman.²² This imposition of the male on the female body is considered a traditional practice in the society, yet due to being forceful and without consent, it becomes an act of violence, which, sadly forms another identity for the protagonist. Her body is violated through overt, institutionalised human behaviour, which is violence according to Silverstein.²³ The speaker's description of her new identity with the phrase 'sad woman-body' is enough to express her reaction to the change. The speaker makes it clear that she was not a part of the decision-making process regarding her own body and fate; so, in effect, she had no control over her own self. She did not wish to

²² Simone de Beauvoir, *The Second Sex*, trans. and eds. H. M. Parshley, (London: Jonathan Cape, 1956), p. 273.

²³ Louis Silverstein, 'The Nature of Violence: A Teaching Guide', *The History Teacher*, May, 1971, Vol. 4, No. 4 (May, 1971), p. 68

be a wife or mother, as it is evident from the text that when she was told that she had grown up, she asked for love. That is why when the husband drags her to the wedding bed behind the closed doors, she feels beaten after going through the ordeal. In this scene of marital violence, she transforms into a woman, who is an essential object for the male to attain self-realisation.²⁴ And to attain this self-realisation, the male ignores her existence as a thinking being. This ignobility is a form of disrespect having deep psychological effect on the speaker.²⁵

The way the speaker refers to her pregnancy is also indicative of her attitude towards the violence committed against her. Usually, motherhood is thought to be the epitome of a woman's existence in a patriarchal society and females there are conditioned to accept and showcase this with a sort of pride, making it a classic case of symbolic violence.²⁶ But the speaker's words show her sufferings from pregnancy; and when the child is delivered, she feels relieved, yet discontent with the condition of her body. The crushing weight of her pregnant body metaphorically illustrates her condition as a victim of symbolic violence in the patriarchal society. Her feeling pitiful is not only physical, but also metaphorical; because it indicates the violence that brought her the identity of a woman and mother.

What is notable is that the speaker refuses to be a victim of this symbolic violence any more by giving in to the norms of the patriarchal society. She rejects gender stereotypes when she stops wearing male approved dresses, refuses to maintain traditional feminine looks, and starts ignoring her 'womanliness'. This new form of resistance is a direct insult, a rejection of the stereotyped images, and offensive to the agents of patriarchy. And these actions lead to the imposition of the established paradigms of an ideal

²⁴ Simone de Beauvoir, *The Second Sex*, trans. and eds. H. M. Parshley, (London: Jonathan Cape, 1956), p. 173.

²⁵ Amartya Sen, "The Nature and Nurture of Violence" p. 61 (Open Book Publishers CIC Ltd., 40 Devonshire Road, Cambridge, CB1 2BL, United Kingdom <http://www.openbookpublishers.com>, Printed in the United Kingdom and United States by Lightning Source for Open Book Publishers)

²⁶ J. Daniel Schubert, "Suffering/symbolic Violence", in *Pierre Bourdieu: Key Concepts*, Grenfell, Michael James, ed. Routledge, 2014. pp.183-4.

woman in a patriarchal society on the speaker. A detailed dress code and career plan is set out for her, the most terrible of which is the instruction to blend in; paying no attention to her own desires. In this fashion the society tries to limit her choice of lifestyle and livelihood.

“... Dress in sarees, be girl,
Be wife, they said. Be embroiderer, be cook,
Be a quarreler with servants. Fit in. Oh,
Belong, cried the categorizers.”

Here “they” are limiting the speaker’s expression, position, and roles in the socio-cultural institutions she is a part of. What they prescribe for the speaker amounts to a constrictive bulwark of patriarchal culture against female assertiveness. The suggested list of what the speaker should become (girl, wife, embroiderer, cook, quarreler with servants) is meant to bind the speaker to a heterosexual domestic foundation. To refuse these is to refuse the sense of belonging and shelter offered by patriarchy. It is notable that no professional or occupational scopes are suggested by the categorisers, who can easily be presumed to be the agents of patriarchy, as if they consider her unable to engage in productive activities. Such limitation, when imposed upon an individual, curbs his/her potential and can be considered as an act of violence.²⁷The categorisers go on to limit her choices of identity to pre-determined formulas which only they can fathom, cutting off her ambit of self-exploration and discovery.

“Be Amy, or be Kamala. Or, better,
Still, be Madhavikutty. It is time to
Choose a name, a role. ...”

If she cannot explore and discover herself, she cannot redefine and reconstruct her own identity. The voices that keep on sanctioning these limitations seem not to understand that a person does not have a singular identity, rather s/he has many. These multiple identities make people who they are. Confining one within a single identity or rejecting all others is

²⁷Johan Galtung, ‘Violence, Peace, and Peace Research’, *Journal of Peace Research*, 1969, Vol. 6, No. 3 (1969), pp. 168-169

extremely violent, as according to Amartya Sen, violence is fomented by the imposition of singular and belligerent identities on gullible people, championed by proficient artisans of terror.²⁸

The voices ravage on:
 "... Don't play pretending games.
 Don't play at schizophrenia or be a
 Nympho. Don't cry embarrassingly loud when
 Jilted in love..."

What is done here is that the authoritative 'they' brings to fore what is typically thought of women in a patriarchal society: women are pretentious, schizophrenics, nymphomaniacs. This is a barely veiled assault to the women in the society, where the patriarchs think that to be woman is a culmination of these qualities. Here is outlined the identity of a woman, framed by the patriarch. The most common assumption regarding a woman is reserved for the last, when a woman is instructed to suppress her emotion after heartbreak; as if she will definitely cry, as if to cry at such cases makes her a woman. Subjecting women to such stereotypical suppositions is an act of violence towards women, but it seems that in patriarchy a woman becomes a woman by accepting such stereotypes.

The speaker is seen struggling to establish her identity throughout the poem. After demolishing the identities assigned to her the speaker reaches the final development of the journey: construction of her identity. Although, the process is lengthy, multi-layered and takes a huge toll on her conscience, she is resilient.

"... I met a man, loved him. Call
 Him not by any name, he is every man
 Who wants woman, just as I am every
 Woman who seeks love. ..."

This is the weary speaker, weary of being branded with names like 'Amy', 'Kamala' or "Madhavikutty"; trying to become a nameless feminine identity.

²⁸ Amartya Sen, *Identity and Violence: The Illusions of Destiny*, (London and New York: Penguin, 2006). p. 15.

Suddenly, the woman who hid her womanliness by wearing her brother's shirt and cutting her hair is no more afraid of her femininity. From here, she becomes one with universal symbols. The feminist activist and author Carol Hanisch's coined slogan, "The Personal is Political" which had become synonymous with the second wave of feminism,²⁹ resonates well with the universalisation in "An Introduction". The personal becomes universal here, as if the speaker is gradually becoming one with the flow of the universe, synergising with nature. For the first time, she takes control and builds a relationship of her own accord. She engages in a love-relationship with a man, but does not specify a person. Not giving the man any name allows the speaker to confine him to a stereotype; this lover is every man who objectifies women as sexual possession. This man and this relationship are highly symbolic. The man is as much a part of this relationship as she is. She goes on to describe the relationship further through metaphors:

"... In him... the hungry haste
Of rivers, in me... the oceans' tireless
Waiting. ..."

What she craves is the identity of a beloved. From her youth she has been searching for love. The violent and impatient love-making only makes the reader realise that her desire remains unfulfilled, her wait to feel loved continues. Although the speaker seems to accept her femininity, actually from here on she begins a violent assertion of her own identity. In patriarchy, females are portrayed as a feminine self which is basically a political perception, serving the agenda of establishing male superiority. This perception ultimately constructs a hegemonised concept where women accept a subordinate position, whereas the male defines himself by the supreme male ego, 'I'. Simone de Beauvoir describes how woman "is determined and differentiated in relation to man, while he is not in relation to her; she is the inessential in front of the essential. He is the Subject; he is

²⁹ http://www.gender.cawater-info.net/knowledge_base/rubricator/feminism_e.htm

the Absolute. She is the Other”.³⁰ The speaker starts refusing to be the object of the male gaze, and turns the table by making the male the object of her gaze. She starts to question “each and everyone.”, but she is not merely asking a question, rather with her questioning, she is doubting and thereby shaking the patriarchal structure to its very roots:

... Who are you, I ask each and everyone,
 The answer is, it is I. Anywhere and,
 Everywhere, I see the one who calls himself I
 In this world, he is tightly packed like the
 Sword in its sheath. It is I who drink lonely
 Drinks at twelve, midnight, in hotels of strange towns,
 It is I who laugh, it is I who make love
 And then, feel shame, it is I who lie dying
 With a rattle in my throat. I am sinner,
 I am saint. I am the beloved and the
 Betrayed. I have no joys that are not yours, no
 Aches which are not yours. I too call myself I.

Here the speaker ultimately comes to terms with her identities. She realises that she is not just a girl or woman, bound to any gendered role in the patriarchal society. She first establishes the male identity as ‘I’ when she says that the answer to her question “Who are you” is always an ‘I’. Then to describe this ‘I’ she deliberately uses the metaphor of a sword in a sheath to show the position of the male in a patriarchy, because in patriarchy it is the privilege of man to own and assert an identity. She notices the liberty ‘I’ has; she watches his activities. But at the same time, she starts asserting her position in the society. It seems that after experiencing enough violence at different stages of her life, the speaker at last has come to terms with her true identities. She develops an identity of an individual being, not that of a woman, or wife, or mother. When she goes on to list what she does, it feels that she is valuing laughing, making love, or feeling shame afterwards with a man having a drink at night in a hotel in a strange town; because they both

³⁰Simone de Beauvoir, *The Second Sex*, trs. “Constance Borde and Sheila Malovany-Chevallier (New York: Vintage Books, 2011), p. 173.

are enjoying the same amount of freedom at last. Inseparably connected to the man, she decimates the difference between 'her' and 'him' and identifies herself as an equal to the symbolic man. She becomes one with the established image of the man. Strangely, this identity comes to her without any violence. Rather it seems that the speaker has made peace with herself. She accepts her sins of desire, but believes that her suffering is like that of a saint. She rejoices the love she has received alongside remembering the pangs of betrayal. She grows into a true individual by sharing the pleasures and pains with the 'I'.

A society where women are made to conform to patriarchal norms, it differentiates between male and female so drastically that transposing the two is not only simple tinkering, but a violent disregard of the established system itself. Throughout its development, "An Introduction" continues to propose the idea that in a society where the hierarchical system is formed and ultimately maintained by the dominant class, which in the context of the poem is the male, identities are formed through violence; while to attain a position of privilege, the dominant class needs only to go about their own lives.³¹The poem's narrative exposes the struggle of an individual with the toxicities of life as she explores and forms her identities through violent experiences. Kamala Das' "An Introduction" documents the violent process of identity formation of a woman in a male dominated society by overcoming suffering, deprivation, and exploitation; and disrupting the established social norms of a patriarchal society by identifying herself with the dominant male 'I'.

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³¹J. Daniel Schubert, "Suffering/symbolic Violence", in Pierre Bourdieu: Key Concepts, Grenfell, Michael James, ed. Routledge, 2014, p. 184.

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